

THE PROHIBITION OF THE USE OF ILLEGAL EVIDENCE AT THE LEVEL OF DECISIONS OF THE EUROPEAN COURT AND THE PRESUMPTION OF INNOCENCE**Khalilov Yunis***Senior lecturer of the chair "Legal studies"
Nakhcivan State University, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

In the article, the prohibition of using illegal evidence at the level of the decisions of the European Court is studied as an important element of the presumption of innocence. The article analyzes the position of the European Court on evidence obtained as a result of violation of privacy, as a result of torture, inhuman or degrading treatment, as well as as a result of incitement to commit a crime (provocation). In the end, it is concluded that the European Court, while stating that the issue of evidence collection is a matter of domestic law, also accepts the need to observe certain limitations regarding the evaluation of evidence obtained as a result of provocation.

Keywords: the presumption of innocence, European Court of Human Rights, sin, provocation, evidence against law

Article 6.2 of the European Convention "On the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms" states that the phrase "until proven guilty by law" can be considered as a referral provision pointing to the national legislation of the states. "Legal proof of guilt" is an important element of the presumption of innocence. This provision acts as a guarantor against the threat of falsification and use of evidence by government authorities, which is one of the most serious issues in the judicial system. Such events can happen in any country. In order to blame for this, we can give an example of the initiation of a criminal case against a person by secretly placing narcotics in his pocket, car and house and perjury against him.

The condition "until proven guilty according to law" reflected in Article 6.2 of the Convention contains an extremely important prohibition: the inadmissibility of using illegal evidence to prove a person's guilt. The Court leaves the question of "proof under the law" to the national law of the States that have ratified the Convention, and it merely examines whether it has been abused. In the decision of June 24, 1988 in the case "Schenk v. Switzerland" [9], it is noted that the provisions of national law that allow the use of evidence collected illegally in the administration of justice are not in themselves considered contrary to the right to a judicial investigation [1].

The European Court does not show an unequivocal position in accepting the principle of not referring to illegally collected evidence when giving a sentence [2]. Among the reasons for this, the first is the absence of a "common European approach" to the issue in question; and the second is the absence of special rules on evidence, especially on the admissibility of evidence, in the Convention [8]. However, we believe that the Court could have determined that the illegally obtained evidence was inadmissible, at least from the standpoint that it violated the constitutional rights of the accused.

If the justice process is viewed as a whole, the use of illegal evidence during the proof of a person's guilt may not harm the right to a fair trial. Thus, the European Court is examining the form of obtaining evidence and the role it plays in the pre-trial stage from the point

of view of whether it makes the entire justice process illegal later. If it does not call into question the objectivity of justice as a whole (that is, if the guilt of a person is proved not by an illegally collected evidence, but by a number of other evidences obtained legally), its illegal acquisition in relation to a specific evidence does not harm the essence of the case.

While discussing the issue of evaluating the use of illegal evidence, it would be appropriate to draw attention to an issue related to the prohibition of torture. Thus, the prohibition of torture is accepted as a norm of *jus cogens* (supreme law) by the European Court, as well as by most international courts. No exception to this prohibition can be defined [4].

There is no provision in Article 3 of the Convention that regulates the question of whether evidence obtained by torture and statements obtained should be evaluated at the time of sentencing. Relying on evidence collected in violation of Article 3 of the Convention, which prohibits torture, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, in itself violates Article 6 of the Convention.

Now let's take a look at the legal consequences of the illegal acceptance and use of evidence in the following categories of rights violations.

2. On illegal evidence according to the type of violated rights

A. Regarding evidence obtained as a result of violation of privacy

The European Court considers the use of evidence obtained through illegal interference in the course of justice to be a violation of privacy.

A concrete answer to the question of whether evidence obtained as a result of violation of privacy can be used in the decisions of the European Court of Justice of June 24, 1988 in the case of "Schenk v. Switzerland" as well as in the case of "Salabiaku v. France" of September 26, 1988 in addition to not giving, he emphasized that Article 6 of the Convention guarantees a fair trial, but there is no provision on the legal validity of an evidence provided that the rights and freedoms protected by the Convention are not violated. Noting that

this is a matter related to the authority of domestic authorities at the level of national legislation, the Court did not define a general rule to be accepted as an abstract and principle on the legal value of an evidence obtained illegally during the trial, i.e. the question of its validity in the proof of guilt, as long as there is no direct violation of the right to a fair trial.

From the decision of the European Court of Justice in the case "Khan vs United Kingdom" dated 12 May 2000, it appears that the applicant Khan was convicted for his involvement in the smuggling of heroin [10]. The reason for his conviction was an audio recording about his involvement in drug smuggling. That audio recording was used as the only evidence in the case. The question that needed to be answered was whether this evidence should be used during the investigation, despite the fact that there is no specific provision in English law for audio recording.

Referring to the "Schenk vs Switzerland" and "Teixeria de Castro vs Portugal" cases, it was stated that it is not within the authorization of the European Court to determine whether the evidence collected by resorting to illegal means will be accepted as proof of guilt. According to the court, the question that needs to be answered is whether the trial, including the method of obtaining evidence, was fair as a whole. This is also related to the need to investigate another violation of the Convention. It is no coincidence that in the mentioned case, the Court decided that Article 8 of the Convention, which provides for the right to respect for private life and family life, was violated, but that Article 6 was not violated. The Court emphasized that the use of secret audio recording does not conflict with the right to a fair trial in Article 6.1 of the Convention.

B. Evidence obtained as a result of torture, inhuman or degrading treatment

The position of the European Court on the mentioned issue is as follows: First, if the evidence was obtained by applying prohibited interrogation methods by subjecting to torture and ill-treatment, the related assessment is examined on the basis of Article 6.2 of the Convention. Second, if the evidence was obtained unlawfully by other than prohibited interrogation methods, as well as in violation of evidentiary prohibitions, then the Court examines whether the right to a fair trial contained in Article 6.1 of the Convention has been violated, taking into account certain criteria.

C. Evidence obtained as a result of incitement to commit a crime (provocation).

In the theory, the terms "instigating agent" and "provocative agent" are also used as the term "incitement to commit a crime" (hereinafter - "provocation") [8]. Incitement here means inciting someone to commit a crime in order to get caught, despite having no direct interest in committing the crime. In particular, this method is used by investigative bodies to arrest persons who have chosen to commit crimes related to the illegal circulation of drugs, which in some cases is considered as inciting a person to commit a crime [3].

The provocation method has been used for hundreds of years. Although the said method has been criticized from various aspects at all times, it always "lives" as the most powerful "weapon" applied by the

investigative bodies of individual states. The institution of provocation remains one of the disputed problems in our modern times as in the past [6].

The purpose of provocation is to obtain evidence that a person has committed a crime. At this time, the presumption of innocence is violated because the evidence collected is not legal. An instigator does not have the right to induce a person to commit a crime, incite him to commit a crime, or influence him in any other way to commit a crime under the pretext of his official authority [7].

Only if it is known that the person will commit the crime by his own voluntary activity, the responsible employees of the criminal prosecution body can take certain tactical measures against him within the powers allowed by the law. During provocation, a person who has no interest and intention to commit a crime is lured into a trap and encouraged to commit the desired crime, while the promotional measures applied at this time not only violate the criteria of legality, but even the said inducement itself is considered a violation of law.

The European Court has commented on the issue of the conditions under which a provocateur agent can induce a person to commit a crime and what the legal consequences of exceeding the limits of provocation will be. In the decision of June 9, 1998 in the "Teixeria vs Portugal" case, the European Court announced its position on the issue of provocation [11]. So, in that case, the officials of the official body entered the role of a conditional buyer in order to seize the persons who provide these substances in the purchase and sale of drugs. At the time of the purchase, a group of people including the applicant was arrested, the applicant was held responsible, and in the end he was charged.

The applicant stated that the police officers did illegal work, committed the crime at the instigation of the authorized persons, did not commit any crime before, there was no trial and preliminary hearing regarding this matter at the beginning, and as a result, the right to a fair trial was violated.

First of all, the European Court noted that the admissibility of an evidence is a matter of national law that is assessed by local courts. The Court further stated that the Convention does not give the Court the duty to determine a specific authority on the issue of whether or not to evaluate the testimony of witnesses. However, the Court examines whether the process was fair, including the manner in which the evidence was obtained.

According to the court, the use of undercover agents during the fight against drug trafficking should be limited and safeguards should be provided in this regard. Undoubtedly, organized crime requires measures to be taken accordingly. But an objective and fair system cannot be sacrificed for the purpose of giving benefits. Public interest cannot justify the use of evidence obtained as a result of police provocation. The court noted that the government did not claim that the police intervention (provocation) was carried out as part of an anti-drug operation on the orders of the judge or with the authority given by the judge. There is no grounded reason for the authorities to suspect that the applicant is a drug buyer or seller. On the contrary, there is a fact that the applicant has not committed a crime before, and

no preparatory investigation has been conducted on him in this case. In fact, this person was never recognized by the police until he was contacted by two other persons (police officers). No drugs were found in the applicant's house.

The authorities did not act passively and did not limit themselves while investigating the criminal act of the applicant. On the contrary, they influenced in the form of instigation [5].

In this case, it was also noted that the verdict handed down by the national court was based on the testimony of two police officers. When all the details of the incident are taken into account, the actions of the police officers exceed the limits of the "secret agent" activity. Because they incited the applicant to commit a crime. Without the intervention (provocation) of the police, the applicant would not have committed the crime, as there was no reason to do so. The Court concluded that the use of evidence obtained as a result of police intervention and provocation in the course of justice "deprived" the applicant of his right to a fair trial from the outset, and that Article 6.1 of the Convention had been violated.

In its decision of December 15, 2005, in the case of Grigory Arkadyevich Vanyan vs Russian Federation, convicted for the crime of drug trafficking, the European Court of Justice ruled that Vanyan's conviction should be based mainly on evidence created by the intervention of the police, especially the courts, including the fact that the Presidium of the Moscow City Court hearing the case in a supervisory manner did not pay attention to the issue of incitement (provocation) by the militia in the case and did not investigate the effect of this provocation on a fair trial and the extent of that effect as a serious defect committed by the Russian courts (40- paragraph) [12].

Taking into account Article 6.1 of the Convention, after examining the evidence of the applicant and the Government of the Russian Federation, and based on its previous experience, especially the decision in the case of "Teixeria de Castro vs Portugal", the Court once again noted that "...the fair trial as reflected in Article 6 of the Convention it follows from the requirement that the public interest in the fight against the sale of drugs cannot justify the use of evidence obtained as a result of police provocation. In the event that the actions of secret agents of the police are aimed at inciting a person to commit a crime, and there are no grounds to show that that person can commit this crime without their (agents') intervention, this situation goes beyond the concept of "secret agent" and can already be called provocation" (Paragraphs 46-47 of the decision).

From all of this, we can conclude that the European Court, in addition to stating that the issue of evi-

dence collection is a matter of domestic law, also recognizes the need to observe certain limitations regarding the evaluation of evidence obtained as a result of provocation.

As can be seen from the decisions mentioned above, the Court declares that the use of evidence obtained as a result of police investigation cannot be justified for public benefit. From here, it is clear that the right to a fair trial is a superior and supreme value that cannot be sacrificed for anything.

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